

Literature Review on the Relationship between Natural Life, Health, and Rehabilitation

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To cite this article: İrfan Çivici Current Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 477 – 499. - 0099-0001-2208-0411.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The magazine is published monthly.

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Georgia”) process. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

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Abstract

It has been a concept since ancient times that certain natural regions have unique properties that can supply pleasure and healing for a distressed soul. The epic of Gilgamesh, written about five thousand years ago, tells how King Gilgamesh could find solace, vitality, and health in a magnificent garden. The love of beautiful nature is conveyed in religious texts such as the Bible and the Koran, in the poems of the Roman writer Virgil, and later in countless poems, novels and songs. However, during this time there were also depictions of unpleasant and unhealthy natural areas; Some of these descriptions arouse fear, which causes people to avoid them. Dante Alighieri's Divina Commedia, published in 1320, uses images of stinging insects, storms, swamps, icing, dark, red-hot deserts, and suffocating vapors to characterize hell. According to studies, people have a natural tendency to avoid certain situations and predicaments, while finding others attractive. The origin of the term "nature" can be traced back to the Latin word "natura", which means "birth". Originally, the term had a wide-ranging meaning and meant a foundation or innate feature of certain objects or people, as well as life on earth or in the cosmos. The term "culture" comes from the Latin word "cultura", which literally means "to cultivate", but can also be interpreted as "care and honor". The word "cultura" comes from the Latin word "colere", which can be translated as "tendency" and "to protect". In his article, Thomas Beck discusses two philosophers of the Renaissance period, Jacopo Bonfadio and Bartolomeo Taegio. Both authors presented their ideas on how nature should be portrayed and perceived in the mid-16th century. This article has been created to examine the relationship between nature and rehabilitation with these and similar examples.

Keywords: *Rehabilitation, what is Rehabilitation? Rehabilitation and Health, Rehabilitation and Healing*

1. Introduction

They decided unspoiled natural areas as the first nature type, cultural landscapes consisting of fields and pastures as the second nature type, and gardens as the third nature type. Beck argues that these ideas are not new but elaborated earlier in ancient Rome by such people as Pliny the Elder, Lucretius, and Cicero, among others. According to Bonfadio and Taegio, the concept of "third nature" expresses the most perfect connection between "nature" and "culture", especially between "art" and "nature". In the field of landscape architecture, a significant emphasis has been placed on this understanding of nature. It is seen that especially the first nature, but also the second and third natures are in danger in today's world. Therefore, there has been a fourth nature discussion, which will involve recreating highly biodiverse ecosystems in both urban and rural settings.

Kronlid writes on the first view of nature that research among landscape architects has shown can be divided into three parts:

"Free nature", completely free to develop under its own conditions without exposure to visible human influence; "unfree nature" used to meet needs, for example in tourism and recreation; and a kind of "fake nature" is a fake construct that is completely subject to human influence as a production environment. "Free nature" is completely free to develop. This tradition is also strong in environmental psychology, and not particularly in areas where environmental psychology, landscape design, and nature's impact on health are integrated; for example, it is real when it comes to nature-based rehabilitation. As Terry Hartig and colleagues write, "We are particularly concerned with nature as seemingly natural aspects and processes that individuals can experience in their daily lives without the need for special tools or sensory aids." (...) The expressions "nature" and "natural environment" may seem like a contradiction. As such, they are often used interchangeably, even though what is important in this context is that nature may not only be found in the natural setting, not only in the environment, but also in situations made otherwise. (...) Although people are aware of the artificial nature of these places, they may consider city parks, botanical gardens, and golf courses as representations of their natural habitats. More work is being

done to explore the health-promoting properties of nature and to decide which properties have the most impact in relation to factors such as age, gender, or health; at work or at leisure; in schools, hospitals, or homes; and such. The term "perceived sensory dimensions" (PSD) refers to one of the ways these attributes can be described.

2. Improving Quality of Life

Earlier studies have found that spending time in natural settings and incorporating nature therapy into rehabilitation programs can improve quality of life, relieve symptoms of stress, reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, and increase a person's ability to return to work after being absent due to illness. Much of this research has been conducted in urban parks, gardens, and other green spaces. However, research has also been conducted in forested areas away from residential areas. According to a considerable number of scientific studies on the subject, forest therapy has been shown to be effective in reducing stress and depression levels in adults. However, most studies do not perform well enough in terms of control groups and accuracy.

based rehabilitation is suitable for men suffering from depression and stress or long-term illnesses that can lead to depression and stress, and we have an expectation that the nature-based "Wild Man Program" can help men.

As a result, we predict that participants who receive the intervention will experience a significant improvement in their quality of life, as measured by the World Health Organization Quality of Life Instruments (WHOQOL-BREF) scale [63]. , which is equivalent to a 20% improvement. The WHOQOL-BREF Quality of Life Scale is an abbreviated and generic version of the Quality-of-Life Scale created by the World Health Organization .

In addition, we hypothesize that there will be significant improvements in other secondary-effect outcomes (stress symptoms, self-experienced reinstatement and return to work) compared to individuals given normal therapy (TAU). To our knowledge, such an intervention or research project has never been done before.

3. Cerebral Palsy

Cerebral palsy is characterized by irregularities in movement and posture, followed by secondary problems such as joint contracture and postural deformity. Cerebral palsy also needs a variety of therapies over an extended period of time. Numerous studies have shown that children with unique health care needs, such as cerebral palsy (CP), have higher rates of unmet health care needs. We believed that the key to solving unmet health care needs is to have an awareness of the current state of care available to children with CP. As a result, we decided to conduct a large-scale study based on NHID's national database in Korea to investigate the type of rehabilitation services offered to children with cerebral palsy and to decide if there were any shifts in patterns in the last ten years. It was discovered to be rehabilitation therapy and BTx. In Korea, it is conducted on patients at a younger age compared to the past. Number of children receiving rehabilitation treatment and BTx. It reaches its maximum between 0-9 years of age, 1 to 5 years of age, and 6 to 7 years of age, respectively. Family income did not have any effect on the amount of money spent on rehabilitation treatment.

Numerous studies have proved the benefits of early diagnosis and initial treatment in children diagnosed with CP. The findings of the current study showed that rehabilitation therapy is now given at a younger age in Korea, which was another finding of the study. According to the findings of this study, the number of patients treated outside the hospital is higher than the number of patients treated in the hospital. While most children receiving inpatient or outpatient rehabilitation treatment occurred between the ages of 4 and 5, therapy costs grew up to the age of 6 and remained stable after this age. Also, the average number of treatments everyone received increased significantly as they got older. This suggests that children who continue to take part in rehabilitation therapy after the age of 4-5 may suffer CP with a degree of deterioration ranging from mild to severe.

BTx, the current health insurance benefit standard allows medication to be given to children diagnosed with CP starting at age two and increasing from there. Recently, BTx. It started at once after a child with CP reached the age of two, which is the minimum age for which insurance benefits can be granted. This is because the minimum age at which insurance benefit is granted is

two years. The number of BTx cases in children born in 2007 was higher than normal. It has been shown to have BTx every year compared to children born in 2004 . It is successful in the treatment of spasticity in children with CP and it is BTx .

The process of treating sick or damaged animals and then releasing them back to their natural habitat is known as wildlife rehabilitation . Rehabilitation of wildlife is beneficial not only for the animals being cared for, but also for the field of conservation medicine because it creates the chance to check wildlife health as well as the prevalence of diseases and pollutant loads. On the other hand, it is historically considered to have negligible effect on the expansion of populations and has not traditionally been recognized as a useful strategy for animal conservation. Raccoons , Painted Tortoises, Blanding 's Tortoises, Snapping Tortoises, and Little Brown Bats were the five case study species we considered across a spectrum of life history strategies to explore whether rehabilitation and release could in some cases directly support population recovery. (i.e., increasing population growth rates). We ran population simulations over a 200-year period while adjusting two parameters :

severe injury (0%, 1%, 2% or 5% of the population); and 2) the number of damaged animals that recovered successfully (0%, 25%, or 50%). The size of the effect of the different rehabilitation scenarios was greatest when added severe injury rates were at their maximum (5%). The species that show the highest population -level response to rehabilitation and release treatments are the species most vulnerable to increased adult injury rates – turtles and bats. We conclude that wildlife rehabilitation can promote in situ recovery and help stabilize declining populations when the following conditions are met:

- 1) injury is an ongoing source of high additive mortality.*
- 2) target population is small.*
- 3) species shows a K-selected life history strategy.*
- 4) rehabilitation can be combined with other interventions, including on-site threat reduction; and*
- 5) rehabilitation efforts do not endanger or limit in situ conservation interventions.*

6) Vortex

"Wildlife rehabilitation " means "treatment and temporary care of injured, sick and displaced native animals followed by the reintroduction of healthy animals to suitable habitats in the wild" (Miller, 2012). Human-wildlife encounters are often the primary reason for referral (Grogan & Kelly, 2013; Molina-López , Maosa , Torres-Riera , Pomarol , & Darwich , 2017; Tribe & Brown, 2000). Treatment of injured wildlife typically focuses on common and common species. The field of wildlife rehabilitation has long been thought of as one run by exceptionally resolute ordinary people; however, veterinarians are becoming more involved in its management (Manire et al., 2017). The discipline of Conservation Medicine is an interdisciplinary field that acknowledges and integrates the relationships between human health, animal health, and ecosystem health. Wildlife rehabilitation and wildlife veterinarians are vital components of Conservation Medicine science (Jakob- Hoff & Warren, 2012; Tabor , 2002). Rehabilitation studies focusing on individual animals , Conservation in Medicine (or One health ; Cleveland , Borner , and Gislason , 2014) can be used to check health indices in a community if performed by the principles outlined. (Carstairs , 2019; Randall , Blitvich , and Blanchong , 2012; Trocini , Pacioni , Warren, Butcher , and Robertson, 2008). Although these interventions may contribute directly to on-site management, it is not yet known whether rehabilitation and release activities alone have an impact on populations (Sleeman & Clark, 2003).

Conservation scientists' activities are primarily focused on the conservation of populations , species, and ecosystems. To do this, they use a variety of toolkits , including population displacements and threat reduction . Studies have focused on evaluating rehabilitation methods (Molony , Dowding , Baker, Cuthill , and Harris, 2006) or finding potential pitfalls, such as inadvertent transmission of disease through inconsistent application of protocols or reintroduction of rehabilitated individuals. Where wildlife rehabilitation and release efforts are represented in ecological and conservation research, studies have focused on evaluating rehabilitation methods (Deem , Karesh , and Weisman , 2001). ("Population-level effects of wildlife rehabilitation and release vary ...") Rehabilitating wildlife has also been defined as the irresponsible use of resources and should instead be directed towards the conservation of biodiversity in their natural environment and the maintenance of landscape connectivity (Albrecht, 1998). This argument

continues to be made , even though it is not clear whether (or how) the money spent on rehabilitating animals can be channeled into immediate on-site solutions (Sikarskie , 1992). When distributing resources according to a conservation science approach, the care of individual animals may not be prioritized as the focus may be on treatments at the population level. In contrast, the work done by wildlife rehabilitators focuses on the individual animal, even if their goal is the restoration of an entire population or species (Aitken, 2018).

4. Natural Environments Cause Various Emotions

Given that natural environments cause a variety of emotions, how can one recover from elevated levels of stress and mental fatigue while in the natural environment? According to research, people have an innate ability to sense danger or safety when in natural situations. Two different theories, Stress Reduction Theory (SRT) and Attention Restoration Theory (ART), both precede this evolutionary approach. Both hypotheses were set up to explain why, for example, taking a walk in a park in the middle of a city can help individuals recover from elevated levels of stress and mental fatigue.

Roger Ulrich , an American environmental psychologist, is credited with the development of SRT . Ulrich argues that although most of us live in urban environments, the human genome has never changed throughout human history. In earlier times, while man was still subject to the laws of nature, he had to place his faith in his most basic emotions, which can be described as unconscious and involuntary physical reactions. Most of the time, we are overflowing with information in today's metropolitan environments, but our basic emotions are not yet adjusting to the changes brought about by these new living conditions. This can lead to emotional hyperactivity as well as problems with emotional control, all of which can result in stress, anxiety, and depression. When we are in natural environments as opposed to urban settings, it is much easier for us to decide when a threat has passed. This allows both our body and mind to disable the sympathetic stress response following the elimination of a threat and then relax and recuperate after the ordeal. However, when it comes to healing and healing, it is essential to experience natural environments without any danger. In the absence of potential dangers, being in nature at once triggers a parasympathetic

physiological response as well as good feelings. This response is associated with feelings of peace, relaxation, comfort, and interest.

The term "attention processes that occur in nature" is what is meant by the acronym "ART", coined by two psychologists Stephen Kaplan and Rachel Kaplan. These cognitive processes work at the perceptual level and have a healing effect. This idea explains how being in nature can be therapeutic and takes two different forms. Supplies definitions for the attention type:

- *focused attention and*
- *soft attention.*

During a typical day, we switch between two types of attention based on the activities and stimuli currently occupying our time. The Attentional Response Theory (ART) is based on the hypothesis that individuals have two different forms of attention, namely directed attention and fascinated attention. When we are working for a specific purpose and need to block out distractions, such as when driving a vehicle or working in an office, we use a type of focus known as directed attention. This requires a significant amount of energy, is a consuming resource that engages executive processes in thinking and can cause fatigue in focused attention. Our attention is drawn to everything that involuntarily fascinates us; we do not have or must choose when to use this ability. It can be difficult to be fascinated because anything that grabs someone's attention blocks any opportunity for introspection. For example, you may be watching an exciting competition in the world of sports right now. On the other hand, most of the objects you meet in nature have a soft quality towards them. Chances are you will see a glint of water or hear a bird's song. You do not need to make any taxation choices; instead, you can relax and take part in the experience. This not only improves our mental ability, but also has a restorative and healing effect on both our body and soul. According to ART , our senses are activated when we are in nature, and when we are, we naturally receive help from the light attraction that allows us to relax and recharge. This concept has been explored in many studies, all showing positive findings [35,36]. On the other hand, various assumptions such as the evolutionary basis of the process and the concept of soft attraction have been questioned.

5. Rehabilitation Activities in Natural Environments

Since ancient times, people have had the concept that certain natural areas have unique properties that can bring satiety and health to a troubled soul, supplying certain benefits to the visitor. According to the Gilgamesh epic written about five thousand years ago, King Gilgamesh was able to find solace, strength, and health in a magnificent garden. The longing for pleasant natural environments has been expressed throughout history in countless poems, novels, and songs, including scriptures such as the Bible and the Koran, the writings of the Roman poet Virgil, and countless poems, novels, and songs following. However, during this time there were also depictions of unpleasant and unhealthy natural areas; Some of these descriptions arouse fear, which causes people to avoid them. Dante Alighieri's *Divina Commedia*, published in 1320, uses images such as stinging insects, storms, swamps, icing, dark, red-hot deserts, and suffocating vapors to characterize hell. According to studies, people have a natural tendency to avoid certain situations and predicaments, while finding others attractive.

The origin of the term "nature" can be traced back to the Latin word "natura", which means "birth". Originally, the term had a wide-ranging meaning and meant a foundation or innate feature of certain objects or people, as well as life on earth or in the cosmos. The term "culture" comes from the Latin word "cultura" which means "to cultivate" but can also be interpreted as "care and honor". The word "cultura" comes from the Latin word "colere", which can be translated as "tendency" and "to protect". In Thomas Beck [12] article, two philosophers of the Renaissance period, Jacopo Bonfadio and Bartolomeo Discusso discuss Taegio. Both authors presented their ideas on how nature should be portrayed and perceived in the mid-16th century. They decided unspoiled natural areas as the first nature type, cultural landscapes consisting of fields and pastures as the second nature type, and gardens as the third nature type. Beck argues that these ideas are not new but elaborated earlier in ancient Rome by such people as Pliny the Elder, Lucretius, and Cicero, among others. According to Bonfadio and Taegio, the concept of "third nature" expresses the most perfect connection between "nature" and "culture", especially between "art" and "nature". In the field of landscape architecture, a significant emphasis has been placed on this understanding of nature. It is seen that especially the first nature, but also the second and third natures are in danger

in today's world. Therefore, there has been a fourth nature discussion, which will involve recreating highly biodiverse ecosystems in both urban and rural settings.

6. After Healing Wild Animals

wildlife rehabilitation has helped partially minimize the projected extinction threat to turtles and bats. Raccoon populations were unaffected by wildlife rehabilitation scenarios because populations were relatively insensitive to the increasing range of adult serious injury rates we simulated. As a result, wildlife rehabilitation scenarios did not have a significant impact on raccoon populations. Rehabilitating ten percent of the damaged wildlife population results in a marginally larger overall population size where adult severe injury rates are between one and two percent (Figure 3). Further depopulation was minimized by rehabilitating larger proportions of the injured (25 percent or 50 percent of the injured). This made the population more likely to endure.

wildlife rehabilitation on populations was greatest at times when the overall adult mortality rate from severe injury was highest (5%). The otherwise declining Painted Tortoise and Little Brown Bat populations have increased (25-50%) due to the successful rehabilitation of large numbers of severely injured animals. Rehabilitation is both Snapping under scenarios with cumulative adult severe injury rates of 2% and 5%, respectively. Turtle and Blanding's for Turtle populations, it increased the chance of population persistence.

Snapping Turtles, Blanding Turtles, and Little Brown Bats are examples of three species that are more likely to have population-level consequences because of wildlife rehabilitation . These species are particularly vulnerable to increases in adult mortality. However, although the range of simulated rehabilitation rates supplies moderate reductions in these cases, Blanding's Turtle and Snapping It did not reverse declines in turtle populations.

welfare of wildlife populations can be improved through the rescue of individual animals. Our findings suggest that wildlife rehabilitation and release have the potential to be a tool for wildlife conservation in certain contexts. This is because extensive rehabilitation efforts have the potential to either stabilize some endangered populations or at least reduce the likelihood of extinction.

Rehabilitation efforts are likely to be beneficial for species with slow life history strategies. In our simulations, the population-level benefit of rehabilitation interventions for species capable of rapid exponential population growth was negligible. Species with slow life history strategies are more likely to receive help from rehabilitation efforts. When damaged wildlife is rehabilitated, either in terms of individual animals or in terms of the population as a whole, the result is a reduction in mortality for injured animals. Therefore, the impact should be comparable to that of a population empowerment program (Kelly et al., 2011; Mullineaux, 2014), even though there may be reductions in fitness among those rehabilitated. Rehabilitation efforts could in theory have a similar effect when applied on a scale sufficient to offset the underlying threats to a species. Population strengthening efforts have prevented several extinctions over the past century (Jachowski and Lockhart, 2009; Jones et al., 2008; Walters et al., 2010). Population strengthening efforts have also prevented several extinctions over the past century. Rehabilitating individual animals is not always a useful method for population stabilization, but neither are most other conservation interventions currently available (such as relocation, breeding in captivity, and releasing offspring). Dodd & Seigel, 1991; Magdalena Wolf, Garland, and Griffith, 1998). If wildlife rehabilitation has the potential to be a useful tool in some situations, conservation research needs to be explicitly included in the toolbox and the efforts of wildlife rehabilitators need to be acknowledged and supported.

7. Adult Rehabilitation

Rehabilitation of a small number of adult individuals had the greatest impact on population persistence in the small populations we modeled in our scenarios for species with longevity, slow maturation, and low fertility. This was the case in the small populations we modeled. Increasing adult mortality rates have the greatest impact on population growth in species with delayed life history strategies, so this result should come as no surprise (Heppell, 1998; Heppell, Caswell, & Crowder, 2000; Wang, Fujiwara, Gao, & Liu, 2019). Where it is impossible to directly minimize the causes of injury and potential death, rehabilitation of injured persons is an effective method to reduce the overall mortality rate. For species where rehabilitation efforts have the

potential to have population -level impacts, we should expect that these impacts will increase as population size decreases. This is because the removal or replacement of an individual has a greater effect in very small-sized populations . Therefore, rehabilitation of individuals has the potential to have an impact on populations and should be considered a conservation measure where population numbers are low (compared to carrying ability), and the species is long-lived.

Our scenarios spanned an extended period (200 years), and the magnitude of the rehabilitation 's impact grew over time. This suggests that sustained rehabilitation efforts will be necessary to have the most impact on an endangered population . Despite this , population sizes of rehabilitation scenarios resulted in larger populations after three generations.

population -level benefits of rehabilitation are optimistic, as we assume that rehabilitated individuals will show comparable fitness (reproduction and survival) to other individuals in the population. Because we assumed that the rehabilitated individuals would be healthier. Although releasing only animals that have reached this level of fitness is considered the gold standard for wildlife rehabilitation (Miller, 2012), this can be difficult to decide in real practice. Considered a type of wildlife displacement (IUCN/SSC, 2013), the practice of treating wild animals in captivity has the potential to alter the behavior and wellness outcomes of animals temporarily or permanently. However, unlike other forms of relocation, rehabilitation is distinguished by the fact that animals are sent back to the place where they were captured rather than sent to an unknown area. Monitoring of rehabilitated individuals after release is necessary to compare the fitness levels of rehabilitated and wild individuals (Gaydos et al., 2013; Kelly, Scrivens , and Grogan , 2010; McWilliams and Wilson, 2015; Saba and Spotila , 2003). Time spent in solitary confinement for rehabilitation may have an impact on mobility and dispersal by increasing displacement (Lyn et al., 2012). This may have an impact on how released animals contribute to the dynamics of local or meta- populations . Procedures for caring for people in captivity can also have an impact on the health of rehabilitated individuals (Davy & Whitear , 2016; Holz , Naisbitt , & Mansell , 2006). To make statistically sound comparisons, it may be difficult to obtain sufficient sample sizes from comparable rehabilitated and non-rehabilitated wild individuals, as well as comparable rehabilitated individuals treated with various methods . These sample sizes are necessary to supply statistically significant findings (Grogan and Kelly, 2013; Hughes, Kennedy, and Litzgus , 2019;

Kelly et al., 2011). However, incorporating the fundamentals of experimental design into considerations of various conservation initiatives, such as rehabilitation or other measures, is essential for setting up best practices (Bennett, Steiner, Carstairs , Gielens , & Davy, 2017; Carstairs et al, 2019). ; Pyke & Szabo , 2018). Our models supply a concise and understandable picture of the possible consequences of wildlife rehabilitation on population levels under a variety of different situations.

Rehabilitating injured or sick wildlife is a vital endeavor that we can all take part in. It is the process of providing care for orphaned, injured, or otherwise sick wild creatures with the goal of eventually releasing the animal back into its natural habitat. This is not something you should try to conduct on your own unless you have the necessary training and experience like that of a veterinarian.

procedure is a pre-release conditioning program that includes the safe capture, examination, and treatment of animals through proper veterinary and hospital care, food, physical therapy, exercise, and medication . The release of the animal must be meticulously adjusted to occur not only when the animal is ready, but also in the proper habitat, location, season, and even weather conditions.

8. Conclusion

wildlife rehabilitation can be an incredibly emotionally challenging experience since there will inevitably be some creatures that cannot be treated and will have to put them to sleep. There will also be animals that can thrive and have good lives, although they may never be released into the wild again. These animals are often housed in zoos, where they serve as teaching tools and are used for important research. In fact, as with anything, there are those who criticize the concept of wildlife rehabilitation because they believe nature should be allowed to take its course; that injured and sick animals should be allowed to be free, and the natural environment should be allowed to dictate the course of their lives ; and rehabilitation of wildlife should be discouraged. However, it should be noted that although this line of reasoning is sound, "nature" is often not responsible for the injuries, illnesses, and deaths of these creatures. Humans are the most common cause of

damage, illness and birth of orphaned wild animals treated in wildlife rehabilitation centres. Some of these may have been accidental, while others may have been deliberate; Examples include high-voltage wires, firearms, cars, trains, lawnmowers, traps, children throwing stones, large windows that are not shut, wood cutters, oil spills, pets, poisons, and anything else that can be harmful to wildlife. A postdoctoral research fellow at the Sydney University Sydney School of Veterinary Medicine and co-author of the paper, Dr. holly Cope said it is important to look at the available data systematically to find factors associated with survival. Dr. holly "Not much is known about these factors for the survival of rescued wildlife," Cope said. "So, it was important to identify factors associated with survival." As natural disasters and severe weather events increase and urbanization continues to spread, an increasing number of animals will need to be rescued and rehabilitated in the future . Staff working with wildlife need to be aware of the data to improve triage and treatment methods. According to the findings of the study, the survival rates of mammals and birds throughout the entire rehabilitation process are comparable; however, survival rates differed depending on location. Forty-five percent of recorded causes of death and injury before or after rescue were attributed to human actions. This includes things like motor vehicle accidents and pet attacks. According to Cope , "human-related activities were generally regarded as an essential component associated with initial injury and long-term survival." [C] ope was the one who conducted the study. "Above all, we must work to reduce these hazards in order to reduce the number of animals in need of rescue." The findings revealed five different categories of factors that can have an impact on the survival outcomes of rescued wildlife and which rehabilitation workers must consider: event (such as an oil spill or fire), individual animal factors (for example, these are nocturnal or diurnal animals in the food chain) , the response performed, the release environment (such as the quality of food or available nesting resources), and the human-wildlife interface. D., an Associate Professor in the School of Life and Environmental Sciences at the University of Sydney and one of the authors of the paper. According to Catherine Herbert, "We need scientists and wildlife rehabilitators to continue working together to learn more about the factors that can lead to more successful rehabilitation outcomes." ("Factors Affecting Survival of Wildlife After Rehabilitation") "We need to learn more about the factors that could lead to more

successful rehabilitation outcomes ,” he said. Finally, we want to supply the best care for the creatures in our responsibility.

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